

PALYNOLOGICAL RESEARCH CONDUCTED IN THE CITY OF TERMIZ

Fayzullaeva Dilaro Botirjon qizi

Sharof Rashidov Samarkand State University Institute of Biochemistry,

PhD student, Department of Botany

Odilova Shakhnoza Khayrulloevna

Termiz Institute of Economics and Service. Faculty of Medicine, Assistant teacher,

Department of Natural Sciences

Abstract: In this thesis, information is given about currently relevant allergic diseases and the factors that cause them, as well as information about some plants that cause allergic diseases identified as a result of aerobiological monitoring in the city of Termiz, and the results of palynological research. passed.

Key words: pollinosis, Lanzoni VPPS 2010 dust trap, aerobiological monitoring, pollen grains, palynology.

Introduction. Currently, targeted measures are being implemented in our country to implement advanced methods of prevention, diagnosis, and treatment of allergic diseases. At the same time, due to climate change, the extension of the pollen season due to global warming, the deterioration of the ecological situation, and other factors, the risk of allergic diseases is increasing.[1]

In particular, the number of people affected by the flowering of plants is growing regularly. This is mainly characteristic of people living in areas with a lot of trees and plants. According to statistics, plant dust is the most common cause of allergies among the people of the world.

However, not all plants and flowers cause this condition. Allergic reactions to plant pollens are called pollinosis ("pollen" means pollen in English).

Causes of pollinosis: known factors that cause this disease include pollen from trees such as poplar, peach, willow, and maple, as well as spinach, oats, mountain

mint, sweet and fragrant sura, corn, wormwood, sunflower and dozens of others. plant flower pollen can be included.

Symptoms of pollinosis: depending on the flowering period of the above-mentioned plants, the disease begins. In this case, it becomes somewhat difficult for the patient to breathe through the nose (sometimes the nose is completely blocked, and the patient breathes only through the mouth), the face becomes pale, the mucous membrane of the nose swells, and symptoms typical of acute flu begin.[2]

Currently, the interest of world scientists in conducting aerobiological monitoring is increasing more and more. A number of scientific researches are being conducted in this regard in our country. As a branch of aerobiology, palynology - the science that studies plant dust - is also rising to a new stage of development..[3]Plants and trees are divided into allergenic and non-allergenic groups. Allergenic and non-allergenic trees and plants of the International Molecular Allergology Center under the Innovative Development Agency announced the list. This is reported by the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation. The center has divided trees and plants into 2 groups: recommended and not recommended for planting., black coral, sylvatic species, snowberry bush, European forsythia, common siren, namatak, common dogwood, magonia, western camellia, eastern biota, prickly spruce, Canadian lilac, chitalpa, silk acacia, turang 27 different plants and trees are included such as il, sumac, sumac, cornus, hawthorn species, calian, blue poplar, red poplar.

Research methods: The research began in February 2024 in cooperation with the International Molecular Allergology Center. At the beginning of March, a dust trap belonging to the center was brought to Termiz city and installed. The research continued with the collection of plant dust and their drying, storage and identification. The obtained weekly data were examined under a microscope and presented to the center. The methods given in the relevant literature were used for dust collection and storage.[4]

Research results: 106 families, 2151 species of plants belonging to 652 genera are included in the state cadastral list of Surkhondarya region. Researches on bioclimatic modeling of endemic and rare species of Surkhondarya region are being

conducted. within the framework of palynological research, the results are obtained using the Lanzoni VPPS 2010 dust trap (Fig. 1) on the side of the International Center of Molecular Allergology.

Figure 1. Lanzoni VPPS 2010 dust cover structure

This device records plant dust and spores of bacteria and fungi in the air for a week on its tape, and special preparations are prepared from the tape, they are examined under a microscope and certain conclusions are drawn. will go. (Fig. 2)

Fig. 2. Detection of dust particles in the MIC-D 30 model microscope.

Summary. Based on the results, we can say that there are the following plants that cause allergies in Termiz city: plantago, rumex, chenopodium, poaceae, cuprecaceae, ulmus, alnus, pinus, picea, tilia, betula, platanus, quercus, fraxinus, corylus, salix, populus, etc.

List of references:

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Sh.M. Mirziyoyevning “Allergik kasalliklarning oldini olish va davolash sifatini oshirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida”gi PQ-371-son qarori, 23.11.2023-yil.

2. .U.Esirgarpov. Pollinoz changga allergiyami?30.11.22.kasallik.uz
3. Z.OJumaeva., B.T Roziev. PRELIMINARY PALYNOLOGICAL RESEARCH IN THE CASE OF SAMARKAND. Сборник статей VII Международной научно-практической конференции, состоявшейся 25 января 2024 года. в г.Петрозаводске
4. Н. Р. Мейер-Меликян, Е. Э. Северова и др Принципы и методы аэропалинологических исследований / . М., 1999. 49 с.